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The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

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Introduction

Human capital within the construction industry in Ireland is made up of a myriad of individuals who each perform a relatively siloed function within the operation and management of construction projects. For instance, most of these individuals are tertiary educated academics (engineers, architects etc.) who do not operate to any great extent outside of the parameters of their own specific knowledge base.

There is, however, one individual who performs the function of ‘lynchpin’ in the entire project management process – the construction manager. This person, often called a ‘foreman’, ‘site agent’ or ‘project manager’ is invariably someone who has progressed through various levels of VET. Without this person’s vocational knowledge and understanding of the operation of all aspects of the construction process, projects would not be achievable within programme or budget.

And yet, the development of this individual almost exclusively begins with the earliest level of engagement in VET – apprenticeship. These individuals, through the course of their working lives, attain the position of construction managers where their vocational experience is vital to the operation of the project team. Therefore, threats to skills cycles impede not only the provision of apprentices and tradespeople but also that of future management supply.

Background

Within any economy the construction industry is a vital sector of industry as it delivers the potential for economic growth via the provision of building and infrastructural needs which the rest of the economy and society requires in order to thrive. In Ireland, the importance of the construction sector cannot be over-stated. It has long been a major provider of employment and by virtue of such has consequently been a “key generator of wealth” for the economy (Forfás, 2013). Therefore, a symbiotic relationship has developed between Ireland’s construction industry and macro economy. This relationship, however, has not always been beneficial to both sides as was seen in the catastrophic collapse of the Irish economy in the mid 2000’s.

A consequence of the above economic downturn was the severe contraction of the construction industry. This led to the inevitable increase in unemployment of construction operatives, tradespeople and professionals. One often over-looked casualty of this was the apprenticeship cohort. In Ireland, traditional apprenticeships have been used as the educational paradigm of construction industry related trades, i.e. the construction labour force. Therefore, when construction employment declined, there was an associated reduction in apprenticeship employment also.

This, however, is not surprising, as Lassnigg (2017) postulates that there is a direct relationship between the demand for apprentices and that of labour generally. Moreover, the

supposition is made that this relationship is cyclically tied to economic performance and therefore exacerbated by periods of economic duress.

Apprentice employment

At peak, before the impact of the aforementioned recession, apprentice employment in Ireland was in excess of 30,000 individuals (2005, n=30,319). With the impact of the economic downturn, this figure declined to just over 7,000 apprentices at its lowest point (2013, n=7,125). This represents a reduction of 76 percent of the total apprenticeship population. Even more stark is the statistic regarding new apprenticeship registrations. Before the recession, new apprentice recruitment was steady, recording in excess of 8,000 individuals annually (2006 peak, n=8,306). However, as with the figures above for apprentice employment, the economic downturn reduced this figure drastically. A reduction of 86 percent from peak to trough occurred in just four years (2010, n=1204).

The significance of this statistic is often overlooked by policy makers. Apprenticeship is not simply a method by which to provide cheap labour in the form of semi-skilled operatives (Franz & Zimmermann, 2002). On the contrary, apprentices are a component of direct construction employment. They are productive in their own right and given the “market driven” nature of this educational paradigm, apprentices produce a benefit for their employers by virtue of their productivity (Mühlemann, Wolter & Wüest, 2009).

Moreover, apprentices provide the basis of a skills-cycle within the construction labour market. Through their training and they supply industry with a mechanism by which to consistently replenish skills availability. Without this cycle the threat of a skills gap is pervasive. The importance of this issue has been noted by the Irish national training authority SOLAS. They have stated that “the availability of qualified tradespersons may become an issue as the recovery in the labour market continues” (Skills & Labour Market Research Unit, 2015).

Implications to management

In addition to the threat of a skills gap, there exists another potential deficit within the labour force, brought about by a lack of apprentices, i.e. the supply of appropriately skilled construction managers.

Even more so than a method of replenishing the skills cycle, apprentices are a foundation occupation of VET. Apprenticeship provides an initial stage of education for individuals who have the capacity to develop and transfer their skills to alternative professions (Mohrenweiser & Backes-Gellner, 2010). Apprentices are a link in the chain of the hierarchical labour force structure within the construction industry (O’Connor & Harvey, 2001). By virtue of their VET route through education and their experiential development, apprentices have the capacity to develop over time from tradespeople to managers (Skills & Labour Market Research Unit, 2008).

Within the traditional construction project management team, all members other than the construction manager traditionally follow tertiary educational routes. Though all vital members of the project team, those such as the architect, engineer and surveyor have all pursued non-VET, academic paths to employment. This siloed manner of learning and delivery of function does nothing to endorse these individuals as suitably effective construction managers.

The task of co-ordination of the construction project and the translation of management decisions into instructions to the labour force is a precarious one as project budgets and programmes are directly affected by the ability of the workforce to deliver value for money. The duty of maintaining time, cost and quality of a project is that of the construction manager; whose role is often under appreciated.

This individual requires a broad knowledge and skillset from which to draw upon, developed preferably through experience. Therefore, the ideal candidate for this role is frequently a person who has followed a route of experiential learning, often beginning with an apprenticeship as explained by Mohrenweiser and Backes-Gellner (2010).

Future labour supply

The skills supply situation outlined above should not be under-estimated. As stated, the obvious negative implication for the Irish construction industry brought about by a decline in apprenticeships is that of a skills deficit. However, lessons may be learned from other countries where this issue has been witnessed.

In the UK, a report published by The Work Foundation (2010), described how skills shortages prevail more than a generation after recommendations were made to invest in labour market skills. This is disturbing given the fact that a recent study of construction firms in Ireland reported that 86 percent of employers already feel that a skills gap is present within the Irish construction industry. More worrying still is that 71 percent of these respondents do not currently employ apprentices thereby compounding the problem of future skills availability (Ó Murchadha & Murphy, 2018).

Regrettably, the information above would seem to indicate that Ireland is facing a potential skills crisis. It is therefore vital that all stakeholders to apprenticeship in Ireland collaborate and act now to ameliorate the potential future skills catastrophe.

Regarding the theme of vocational education and training across the lifespan, it is obvious that apprenticeship potentially delivers a springboard from which to develop lifelong learning. However, the issue is academic if the opportunities for initial skills development do not exist.

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Minutes

A presentation of the above paper was made by the author to a workshop of VETNET researchers. The session was moderated by Prof. Michael Gessler. Prof. Gessler introduced the presentation by summarizing the Irish economic context in relation to VET training and, apprenticeship. He further reminded those present of the VETNET meeting in Dublin in 2016 where the impact of recession upon VET training had been discussed. This introduction set the background for the presentation and paper.

Upon completion of the presentation, the assembled participants were instructed to discuss the details and findings presented and to consider the questions posed at the end by the presenter. These questions were as follows:

Q1: Can macro/exo level mechanisms be used to prevent skills deficits occurring?

Q2: How can employer engagement in apprenticeship be maximized?

Q3: Should management level occupations be filled via tertiary level education only, to avoid a skills deficit?

Feedback from the floor was collected via Mentimeter which was overseen and collated by Prof. Barbara Stalder. The author and presenter then answered those questions which were particularly relevant and pertinent to the discussion at hand in the workshop.

Attending researchers at the workshop made relevant statements in relation to several factors regarding the issues raised in the presentation. Notable points included the following:

- IVET was highlighted as a mechanism to offset future skills deficits through early adoption of VET skills.
- The need for state subsidization of employers (particularly micro-firms) was noted as a measure to improve employer engagement in training thereby limiting the potential for deficits in skills availabilities.
- Additionally, the question arose as to why/how employers would/could engage in apprenticeship training.

These issues are considered in the concluding remark below

Conclusions

The traditional apprenticeship system in Ireland, the Standards Based Apprenticeship is connected for the most part either directly or indirectly with the construction industry. Therefore, the current range of apprenticeships in Ireland differs greatly than most European states in that it is not extensive but rather limited in scope. However, this 'limitation' has resulted in the evolution of apprenticeship in Ireland as a specialized paradigm for the delivery of key skills for industry. Through this specialization the construction manager has emerged as a highly competent individual based upon his/her vocational training and work-based learning. This is not a scenario which is easily replicated in a non-VET paradigm of learning. Due to the nature of the experiential learning and tacit skills acquisition of tradespeople, the cycle of skills through apprentice-tradesperson-manager is a form of CVET.

An analogous issue to that of a limited range of apprenticeship, is Ireland's position in terms of IVET. Since Ireland has a standardized post-primary educational route, IVET at upper secondary level is not an available option to commence preparatory VET skills formation. Apprenticeship is the most prevalent form of VET in Ireland, and in its current guise is a post-secondary form of education. The option, therefore, to offset future skills gaps by commencing skills formation at secondary level is not currently possible within Irish VET.

As outlined in the presentation and paper, the impact of the lack of skills upon the pillars of commerce (*time, cost & quality*) is potentially detrimental to the industry. Skills deficits negatively affect the capacity to deliver upon time and quality thereby increasing the cost factor of projects. This is an obvious detraction to any business model but is particularly egregious to the construction industry. This is because the construction industry in Ireland not only relies earnestly upon its ability to respond to the needs of society but more importantly to the demands of foreign direct investment. If the industry is unable to deliver value for money, then investors

will simply go elsewhere. Value for money is symbiotically linked to the availability of requisite skills.

Given the importance of experientially developed construction management skills in achieving value for money and the critical role of the VET skills cycle in the formation of these skills, it is vital that the skills agenda be addressed at the highest level. Although Ireland has a small apprenticeship training sector, it has nonetheless developed very robust social partnerships in the delivery of VET skills. However, given the socio-ecological nature of the apprenticeship structure, and the fact that macro-level policy mandates the delivery of standards in Ireland, State level intervention is required to effect change.

The onerous nature of legislative obligations upon employers has caused a reluctance amongst firms to invest in VET. This is understandable given that most firms in the Irish construction industry employ ten people or less. Therefore, when considering that there currently exist no incentives to employ apprentices in Ireland, macro-level mechanisms should be implemented whereby those employers willing to invest in VET are entitled to either fiscal rewards or taxation exemptions as an incentive to engage in training.

There are potential rewards for all stakeholders. At micro-level, the apprentice receives training, education and employment. At meso-level, the employer gains productivity and is socially responsible, a trait from which there are many benefits to exploit, not least of all in terms of industry promotion. At exo-level, the educational facilities are further engaged in didactic activity. But most importantly, at macro-level the state receives possibly the greatest benefit of all. In Ireland, apprentices are immediately classified as employees and not as students. Therefore, those individuals who gain employment via apprenticeship are productive to society, industry and the economy. Furthermore, as many apprentices would otherwise potentially fall into the category of NEETs, VET training removes them from placing a social welfare burden upon the state in the form of unemployment benefit.

Additionally, there is a need for a paradigm shift in the delivery of VET regarding employer engagement. Traditionally, an employer undertook to train apprentices within his/her firm for the duration of the apprenticeship, relatively confident in the firm's ability to deliver the necessary training due to an adequate supply of work. Today, however, that confidence is lacking, and firms appear unwilling to invest in VET due to the onerous obligations involved by being an employer. This is exacerbated by the fact that the vast majority (>90%) of construction industry employers are micro-firms, employing less than 10 people. Moreover, most of these micro-firms are sole-traders. Since the industry is built upon such micro-firms, these are the potential employers who should be the target of incentivization by the state regarding VET engagement.

As discussed via the associated presentation to the above paper, a large cohort (39%) of employers are undecided regarding their future involvement in training apprentices. It is reasonable to surmise that there are employers within this group who would potentially engage in training but are discouraged by the associated obligations discussed above. As these firms are likely to be in the category of micro-firms already mentioned, it is possible that a significant deterrent to their engagement in training is an uncertainty regarding the availability of sufficient work to support the employment of an apprentice.

Therefore, the above-mentioned paradigm shift is for employers to engage in shared apprenticeship training. The benefits are numerous. Apart from an obvious increase in apprenticeship training numbers, the micro-firm employers could deliver training in a smaller range of work-type and specialization, with the apprentice receiving the full range of requisite work-based learning from the larger co-operative of employers. Furthermore, the onerous obligations involved in being an employer would be significantly reduced when the responsibilities are shared, yet each firm still benefits from the associated productivity of an additional employee.

By exploring such possible interventions in apprenticeship engagement, employers can experience tangible benefits to the firm through VET. As discussed, apprenticeship training via

the natural skills cycle does not only deliver greater productivity but also proactively prepares the firm for future management skills requirements. As such, engaged employers can greatly increase the capacity of the industry to meet the needs of the economy and investors, future proof skills availability, and display great prudence and altruism via the social responsibility shown through employment of apprentices.

Report on the VETNET research workshop
during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018

Vocational education and training across the lifespan

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Introduction

VETNET mission

The Vocational Education and Training Network VETNET is an open network, which welcomes contributions from all over the world as long as they are in line with the goals of VETNET.

VETNET is focusing on research and development in the field of initial, higher and continuing vocational education and training (VET) and learning across the life-span.

The goals of VETNET are to promote research on vocational education and training and to contribute its development by:

- fostering a high quality of research in the field of vocational education and training;
- exploring the relationship between research, policy and practice;
- stimulating the multidisciplinary discussion and dissemination of research results in the European research area and beyond through mutual learning;
- encouraging, establishing and maintaining cooperation between VET researchers and project partnerships in the European research area through, e.g., organising the VETNET programme at the ECER, Crossing Boundaries or Stockholm International Conference; developing international contacts; cooperating with other relevant conferences; publications or by producing electronic or other newsletters;
- maintaining the peer-reviewed VETNET journal IJRVET, the VETNET ECER proceedings and contributing to other international publications; maintaining the community website vetnetsite.org.

VETNET

- maintains a community website on vetnetsite.org;
- has an entry on the EERA website: <https://eera-ecer.de/networks/2-vocational-education-and-training-vetnet/>;
- has a project on [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training): <https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training>;
- has a community on <https://zenodo.org/communities/vetnet/> to host the conference proceedings.

Aim and scope of the workshop

The topic of the researchers' workshop at the EU Vocational Skills Week 2018 in Vienna was: "Vocational education and training across the lifespan".

All participants contributed to the workshop with a short abstract on the topic "Vocational education and training across the lifespan" and a short bibliography.

Four presentations were selected as impetus presentations. These were short presentations by the authors to stimulate the discussion in the workshop. After the discussion, the presenters of the impetus presentations wrote short minutes on the discussion during the workshop. The impetus presentations and minutes are covered in this report.

Programme of the workshop

Introduction

- Dr Christof Nägele
Senior Researcher, University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Northwestern Switzerland
- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler
Professor, Institute Technology and Education, University of Bremen
- Mantas Sekmokas
Policy Officer, European Commission, DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

Impetus Presentations

Lifelong learning and VET: towards understanding the influence of societal eco-systems on learning across the lifespan

- Dr Natalia (Natasha) Kersh
UCL Institute of Education, University of London
- Dr Karen Evans
Professor Emeritus, UCL Institute of Education, University of London

Apprenticeship Reform in France

- Eric Dumartin
Vice-President of Fongecif Île-de-France, Vice-President of IAE Paris I Panthéon Sorbonne

The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

- Eoghan Ó Murchadha
Assistant Head of Department of Craft, Design, Construction and Apprenticeship, Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute in Dublin

The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

- Dr Patricia Olmos Rueda
Professor, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
- Dr Fernando Marhuenda
Professor, University of Valencia

Outlook

- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler & Dr Christof Nägele